

Genetic Variability Analysis for Plant Selection in Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.) in Chhattisgarh Plains

Devendra Upadhyay^{1*}, Dhananjay Sharma¹ and Neeraj Shukla¹

¹Department of Vegetable Science, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Brinjal an important vegetable can grow through the year. Fruits are found in varying colours like purple, green, white and their combinations. Rich in medicinal properties as well as broad genetic base. The experiment was conducted during *Kharif* 2020-21 at the Research cum Instructional Farm, Dau Kalyan Singh College of Agriculture and Research station Bhatapara, I.G.K.V., Chhattisgarh. Variability among the genotypes were highly significant for all the yield component character. The magnitude of PCV was higher than the corresponding GCV for all the traits. High genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation were recorded for most of the characters except plant spread, number of primary branches per plant, plant height and days to first fruit harvest. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percentage of mean were observed for number of fruit per cluster followed by numbers of fruits per plant per picking, fruit yield per plant, fruit yield per hectare, average fruit weight, number of clusters per plant, fruit length, numbers of fruits per plant, pericarp thickness and numbers of flowers per inflorescence.

Keywords: Genotype, Variability, plant selection, fruits

*Corresponding author: E-mail devendracg@rediffmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.), one of the most popular and principal vegetable crops grown in India and other parts of the world which belongs to the family *Solanaceae*. Eggplant was known to India from ancient times [1] and is may be a native of India [2], hence, broad genetic diversity found in plains and plateau. Brinjal is a nutritious vegetable fairly good source of all essentials elements, including calcium, iron, phosphorus and vitamins specially 'B' complex. Vavilov [3] advocated that wide range of variability provides better scope of selecting desirable genotypes. The study of genetic variability was made for the first time by the great biologist Fisher [4]. Genetic parameters such as genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), heritability (h^2) and genetic advance (GA) are commonly used in describing the variability and genetics of a character. Heritability in broad sense may be defined as the ratio of genetic variance to phenotypic variance [5]. Chhonkar et al. [6] reported that heritability estimates and genetic advance were more valid for selection than heritability estimates alone. Hence, in crop improvement programme, there is a need to explore the genetic nature of the plant material that can be carried out with the help of variability parameter.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted during *Kharif* 2020-21 at the Research cum Instructional Farm, Dau Kalyan Singh College of Agriculture and Research station Bhatapara, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Chhattisgarh, India. 35 genotypes (Table 1) were transplanted in a randomized block design with three replications. Every replication comprised of 35 genotypes. Each plot comprised of two rows of 6 m long and 10 plants in each line. The spacing given was 75 cm between rows and 60 cm between plants inside a line. Five arbitrarily tagged competitive plants from every entry were labeled and observations on sixteen characters *viz.* days to 50 per cent flowering, days to first fruit harvest, plant height (cm), plant spread (cm), number of primary branches per plant, number of clusters per plant, number of flowers per inflorescence number of fruits per cluster, number of fruits per plant, fruit length (cm), fruit girth (cm), average fruit weight (g), pericarp thickness (mm), number of fruits per plant per picking, fruit yield per plant (kg) were recorded on labeled plants only. The

data were subjected to the analysis of variance for Randomized Block Design as suggested by Panse and Sukhatme [7].

3. RESULTS

Analysis of variance for fruit yield and its component characters are presented in Table 2 for all genotypes under study that is parents, testers and check. Data as per the table revealed that mean sum of square due to genotype found highly significant for the traits *viz.* days to 50 percent flowering, days to first fruit harvest, plant height, plant spread, number of primary branches per plant, number of clusters per plant, number of fruits per inflorescence, number of fruits per cluster, number of fruits per plant, fruit length, average fruit weight, pericarp thickness, number of fruits per plant per picking, fruit yield per plant, fruit yield per hectare. The genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variations are presented in Table 3. The genotypic coefficient of variation helps to measure the range of genetic variability in character and provides measure to compare the genetic variability present in various quantitative characters.

3.1 Variability

High genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation were recorded for characters *viz.*, average fruit weight (52.24 and 53.11%), number of fruits per cluster (48.78 and 49.36%), fruit yield per plant (39.64 and 40.15%), fruit yield per hectare (39.61 and 40.25%), number of fruits per plant per picking (38.27 and 38.75%), pericarp thickness (36.39 and 37.50%), number of fruits per plant (33.70 and 34.67%), number of clusters per plant (32.70 and 33.30%), fruit length (31.42 and 32.32%), number of flowers per inflorescence (30.51 and 31.49%) and fruit girth (22.71 and 23.54%). For trait plant spread genotypic coefficient of variance (19.34%) and phenotypic coefficient of variance (20.13%) was recorded *i.e.* moderate and high coefficient of variation respectively.

Moderate genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation were noted for traits *viz.*, number of primary branches per plant (18.88 and 19.69%) and plant height (14.59 and 15.85%). For trait days to 50 percent flowering genotypic coefficient of variance (7.53%) and phenotypic coefficient of variance (10.24%) was noted *i.e.* low and moderate coefficient of variation respectively.

Low genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of

variation were recorded for trait days to first fruit harvest (7.48 and 9.50 percent). The results of GCV and PCV of the present study was closely accordance with the finding of Naik [8], Ambade [9], Muniappan et al. [10], Ansari et al. [11], Dhaka and Soni [12], Lokesh et al. [13], Singh et al. [14], Arunkumar et al. [15], Vidhya and Kumar [16], Singh and Singh [17], Sujin et al. [18], Shilpa et al. [19] and Siva et al. [20].

3.2 Heritability

The estimates of broad sense heritability are presented in Table 3. The highest heritability was recorded for number of fruits per cluster (97.67 %) followed by number of fruits per plant per picking (97.54 %), fruit yield per plant (97.46 %), fruit yield per hectare (96.85%), average fruit weight (96.72%), number of clusters per plant (96.46%), fruit length (94.53%), number of fruits per plant (94.49%), pericarp thickness (94.20%), number of flowers per inflorescence (94.11%), fruit girth (93.06%), plant spread (92.24%), number of primary branches per plant (91.94%) and plant height (84.73%) indicating predominance of additive gene action and less influenced by environment factors for expression of these traits. This being fixable in nature considerable progress is expected through appropriate selection scheme to be adopted. Moderate heritability found for days to first fruit harvest (62.04%) and days to 50 percent

flowering (54.01%). This closely follows the findings of Prasad et al. [21], Naik [8], Ram et al. [22], Ambade [9], Muniappan et al. [10], Singh et al. [14], Arunkumar et al. [15], Madhavi et al. [23], Singh and Singh [17], Shilpa et al. [19] and Siva et al. [20].

3.3 Genetic Advance

Genetic advance as percentage of mean is presented in Table 3. High genetic advance as percent of mean was observed for average fruit weight (105.82%) followed by number of fruits per cluster (99.31 %), fruit yield per plant (80.62%), fruit yield per hectare (80.30%), number of fruits per plant per picking (77.86 %), pericarp thickness (72.76%), fruit length (62.93%), number of fruits per plant (67.47%), number of clusters per plant (66.17%), number of flowers per inflorescence (61.04%). Whereas, moderate genetic advance as percent of mean was observed for fruit girth (45.12%) followed by plant spread (38.25%), number of primary branches per plant (37.30%). Traits plant height (27.66%), days to first fruit harvest (12.14%) and days to 50 percent flowering (11.40%) were recorded low genetic advance as percentage of mean. These results are similar with the findings of Ambade [9], Muniappan et al. [10], Dhaka and Soni [12], Singh et al. [14], Arunkumar et al. [15], Madhavi et al. [23], Singh and Singh [17], Shilpa et al. [19] and Siva et al. [20].

Table 1. Genotypes under study (Parents, check, and crosses)

S. No.	Genotype/ F ₁ population	S. No.	Genotype/ F ₁ population
1	IGB-03	19	IGB-16 X IBWL
2	IGB-16	20	IGB-17 X UA
3	IGB-17	21	IGB-17 X UK
4	IGB-24	22	IGB-17 X PPL
5	IGB-50	23	IGB-17 X IBWL
6	IGB-76	24	IGB-24 X UA
7	Utkal Anushree	25	IGB-24 X UK
8	Utkal Keshri	25	IGB-24 X PPL
9	Pusa Purple Long (Check)	27	IGB-24 X IBWL
10	Indira Brinjal White Long	28	IGB-50 X UA
11	Pant Rituraj ©	29	IGB-50 X UK
12	IGB-03 X UA	30	IGB-50 X PPL
13	IGB-03 X UK	31	IGB-50 X IBWL
14	IGB-03 X PPL	32	IGB-76 X UA
15	IGB-03 X IBWL	33	IGB-76 X UK
16	IGB-16 X UA	34	IGB-76 X PPL
17	IGB-16 X UK	35	IGB-76 X IBWL
18	IGB-16 X PPL		

Table 2, Analysis of variance for fruit yield and its component in brinjal

S.No.	Source	Replication	Treatment	Error	SEm	CD at 1%
	Degrees of freedom	2	34	68		
1	Days to 50 percent flowering	6.2310	67.641**	14.953	2.23	8.37
2	Days to first fruit harvest	6.2250	103.371**	17.511	2.42	9.05
3	Plant height (cm)	13.2070	274.64**	15.56	2.28	8.54
4	Plant spread (cm)	4.6120	563.252**	15.37	2.26	8.48
5	Number of primary branches per plant	0.853*	8.337**	0.237	0.28	1.05
6	Number of clusters per plant	0.7140	46.214**	0.558	0.43	1.62
7	Numbers of flower per inflorescence	0.0020	5.176**	0.106	0.19	0.7
8	Number of fruits per cluster	0.0430	6.685**	0.053	0.13	0.5
9	Number of fruits per plant	0.3550	52.346**	0.999	0.58	2.16
10	Fruit length (cm)	1.970	103.736**	1.964	0.81	3.03
11	Fruit girth (cm)	3.1490	47.603**	1.154	0.62	2.32
12	Average fruit weight (g)	18.4890	17324.805**	193.778	8.04	30.12
13	Pericarp thickness (mm)	0.3470	18.028**	0.362	0.35	1.3
14	Number of fruits per plant per picking	0.3910	27.578**	0.23	0.28	1.04
15	Fruit yield per plant (kg)	0.0220	2.026**	0.017	0.08	0.29
16	Fruit yield per hectare (q)	201.3840	100087.027**	1072.836	18.91	70.87

*and ** Significant at $P= 0.05$ and 0.001 levels respectively

Table 3. Genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variations (GCV and PCV), Heritability (h^2), Genetic advance as % of mean and components of Variance for fruit yield and its component characters

S. No.	Characters	GCV %	PCV %	Variance		Mean X	Heritability (%)	Genetic Advance	Genetic advance as % of mean
				Genotypic	Phenotypic				
1	Days to 50 per cent flowering	7.53	10.24	17.56	32.52	55.68	54.01	6.345	11.40
2	Days to first fruit harvest	7.48	9.50	28.62	46.13	71.49	62.04	8.68	12.14
3	Plant height (cm)	14.59	15.85	86.36	101.92	63.71	84.73	17.622	27.66
4	Plant spread (cm)	19.34	20.13	182.63	198.00	69.89	92.24	26.736	38.25
5	No. of primary branches per plant	18.88	19.69	2.70	2.94	8.7	91.94	3.246	37.30
6	No. of clusters per plant	32.70	33.30	15.22	15.78	11.93	96.46	7.893	66.17
7	No. of flowers per inflorescence	30.54	31.49	1.69	1.80	4.26	94.11	2.598	61.04
8	No. of fruits per cluster	48.78	49.36	2.21	2.26	3.05	97.67	3.027	99.31
9	No. of fruits per plant	33.70	34.67	17.12	18.12	12.28	94.49	8.284	67.47
10	Fruit length (cm)	31.42	32.32	33.92	35.89	18.54	94.53	11.665	62.93
11	Fruit girth (cm)	22.71	23.54	15.48	16.64	17.33	93.06	7.82	45.12
12	Average fruit weight (g)	52.24	53.11	5710.34	5904.12	144.67	96.72	153.092	105.82
13	Pericarp thickness (mm)	36.39	37.50	5.89	6.25	6.67	94.20	4.852	72.76
14	No. of fruits per plant per picking	38.27	38.75	9.12	9.35	7.89	97.54	6.143	77.86
15	Fruit yield per plant (kg)	39.64	40.15	0.67	0.69	2.06	97.46	1.664	80.62
16	Fruit yield per hectare (q)	39.61	40.25	33004.73	34077.57	458.67	96.85	368.306	80.30

Fig. 1. Genetic parameters

4. CONCLUSION

In the experiment, the variability among the genotypes was highly significant for all the yield component characters that were useful for improvement in brinjal. The magnitude of PCV was higher than the corresponding GCV for all the traits. This might be due to the interaction of the genotypes with the environment to some degree or due to environmental factors influencing the expression of these traits. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as percentage of mean were observed for number of fruit per cluster, numbers of fruits per plant per picking, fruit yield per plant, fruit yield per hectare, average fruit weight, number of clusters per plant, fruit length, numbers of fruits per plant, pericarp thickness and numbers of flowers per inflorescence indicating that most likely the heritability is due to additive gene effects and selection may be effective.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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